

Comparative Evaluation of Bioethanol Potential of Selected Agro-Wastes obtained From a Farm in Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria

¹Bala, A. *, ¹Shabanda, I. S., ¹Hassan, A. M., ¹Elinge, C. M., ¹Haruna, Y. and ²Muhammad, M. J.

¹Faculty of Physical Sciences, Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero

²Department of Chemistry, School of Physical Sciences, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State

*Correspondence: abalakoko@gmail.com; +234703012911

Submission: 29th December, 2024; Accepted: 10th January, 2025; Published: 14th February, 2025

Abstract

Agricultural wastes, often considered non-productive byproducts, may contain valuable substances. With growing environmental concerns over fossil fuel use and resource depletion, there is a shift toward renewable energy sources. This study investigated the proximate composition and bioethanol production potential of sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells obtained from a farm in Aliero, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Proximate analysis followed AOAC standard methods, and bioethanol production involved dilute H₂SO₄ hydrolysis (2 M) at 121°C for 15 minutes. Significant differences (P<0.05) were observed in proximate composition: carbohydrate content was highest in doum palm shells (67.18%), followed by sweet potato peels (51.32%) and watermelon rinds (32.57%). FTIR analysis confirmed key ethanol functional groups, with O-H, C-H, and C=O peaks. Fuel property analysis showed significant variations (P<0.05), except for specific gravity. Flash points were 55.20°C (SPP), 47.60°C (WMR), and 45.90°C (DPS), while boiling points were 73.60°C, 78.00°C, and 62.80°C, respectively. These results suggest that the studied agricultural wastes have potential as bioethanol sources, which could be blended with conventional fuels. Further research is recommended to evaluate their suitability for combustion engines.

Keywords: Agricultural waste, Bioethanol, Fermentation, Proximate.

1.0 Introduction

Agricultural wastes encompass the leftover materials generated during the cultivation and processing of raw agricultural goods, including fruits, vegetables, meat, poultry, dairy products, and crops [1]. These residues represent the non-productive outcomes of agricultural production and processing, potentially containing substances beneficial to humans. However, their economic value is often lower than the expenses incurred for their collection, transportation, and processing for practical use [2]. The composition of these wastes varies depending on the agricultural system and activities involved, existing in liquid, slurry, or solid forms. Referred to as agro-waste, these residues consist of animal by-products (such as manure and animal carcasses), waste from food processing (with 80% of maize being discarded), crop leftovers (such as corn stalks, sugarcane

bagasse, fruit and vegetable drops, and prunings), as well as hazardous and toxic agricultural waste like pesticides, insecticides, and herbicides [3]. Global concerns have arisen due to the environmental challenges linked to the excessive reliance on fossil fuels, escalating energy needs driven by a growing world population, and the gradual depletion of current energy resources [4]. This situation has prompted the exploration of renewable energy sources that are more environmentally friendly and sustainable. Agricultural residues contain nutrients, cellulose and hemicellulose, making them viable for livestock feed and bioethanol production [5]. This research aimed at comparing the proximate composition and bioethanol production potential of sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds and doum palm shells.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Aliero is located in the southeast of Kebbi State within latitude (12° 16' 42" E and longitude 4° 27' 6" N), the name Aliero was originally derived from two prominent Fulani scholars Ali and Yero. The town is the headquarters of Aliero Local Government Area, an area of 350 km² and population of 65,973 as at 2006 census. Most of the people of the town are Agararian, with emphasis on vegetation, especially onion and pepper. The town has the largest onion market in Northwestern Nigeria [6].

2.2 Sample collection/pre-treatment

Samples of watermelon rinds, sweet potato peels, and doum palm shells were collected from a local market in Birnin Kebbi metropolis on the 20th of February, 2024. The mechanical pre-treatment was conducted on each sample by picking any foreign substances to ensure all the samples are clean and free of dirt. Samples were then air-dried and using standard milling machine, each sample was pulverized into powder and sieved using fine pore separators.

2.3 Proximate Composition

Proximate parameters such as moisture content, ash content, crude protein, crude fibre and carbohydrate were carried out according to the Association of Analytical Chemist (AOAC), methods of analysis [7].

2.3.1 Determination of ash content

About 8g of finely ground dried sample was weighed into a porcelain crucible and incinerated at 550 °C for 6 hours in an ashing muffle furnace (Size 1 (1000°C), Gallenkamp, England) until ash was obtained. The ash was cooled in a desiccator and reweighed. The % ash content in the sample would be calculated as follows using equation 1:

$$\text{Ashcontent}(\%) = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_1} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where;

W1 = weight of original sample before ashing

W2 = weight of sample after ashing

2.3.2 Determination total moisture content

The moisture content of the samples was determined in an oven by dried method (at 105 °C) as described by AOAC. The moisture contents of the samples was determined by weighing 2g of sample into a known weight of filter paper and dried in an air forced draft oven at a temperature of 105 ± 5 °C till the constant weight of dried matter was obtained. The moisture content would be determined from equation 2.

$$\text{Moisturecontent}(\%) = \frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_1} \times 100 \dots\dots 2$$

Where;

W1 = weight of original sample before drying

W2 = weight of dried sample after drying

2.3.3 Determination of crude fibre

Ten grams (10 g) of sample was weighed into 500 cm³ beaker and 200 cm³ of boiling 0.255 mol/dm³ tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid (1.25 percent w/v) was added. The mixture was boiled for 30 min kept the volume constant by the addition of hot water at frequent intervals (a glass rod stirrer was placed in the beaker to enable smooth boiling). At the end of the period, the mixture was filtered through a muslin cloth and the residue washed with hot water till free from acid. The material was then transferred to the same beaker and 200 cm³ of boiling 0.313 mol/dm³ (1.25 percent w/v) NaOH was added. After boiled for 30 minutes, the mixture was filtered to a crucible, dried overnight at 80-100 °C and weighed. The crucible was placed in a muffle furnace at 550 for 3 hours and then allowed to cool in a desiccator and weighed again. The difference in residue weights and ash was taken as the weight of crude fiber.

2.3.4 Determination of crude protein

Exactly 0.5g of sample (dried) was weighted into 500 cm³ Kjeldahl flask; 20 cm³ of concentrated tetraoxosulphate (VI) acid was added gently to each of the samples in the flask and heated on a heating block starting with a low heat about 200 °C for 30 minutes and swirled by shaking the Kjeldahl flask occasionally to mixed and dissolve well. The temperature was increased to about 335 °C and was heated for about 5-6 hours to obtain a clear digest (complete digestion). Then it would be switched off and allowed to cool, and diluted with 100 cm³ of distilled water. 10 cm³ of boric acid was added into 100 cm³ collection flask with 2

drops of mixed indicator and placed under the collection spigot of the distillation apparatus. The digest (10cm³) was pipetted into the micro-distillation apparatus and 10 ml of sodium hydroxide was added gently into the micro-distillation apparatus to react with the sample. The solution was allowed to distil for about 5 minutes or when the volume of ammonia collected in boric acid in the receiver flask is 50 cm³ and the purple had turned green in colour. The distillate was titrated against 0.1 mol/dm³ hydrochloric acid to give a reddish color. A blank titration was carried out and percentage protein calculated using equation 3.

$$\begin{aligned} \% \text{ crudeprotein} &= \%N \times 6.25 \\ &= M \times \frac{V}{w} \times 14gN \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 3 \end{aligned}$$

Where: M = molarity of HCl (mol/dm³)

V = corrected volume of acid (mol std. acid for sample – mol std. acid for blank)

W = weight of sample digested

14 = atomic weight of nitrogen

2.3.5 Determination carbohydrate content

The method described [8] was employed for the determination of carbohydrate. 0.5 mg of the sample was carefully stirred with 0.5 cm³ of ice cold, 80% H₂SO₄ was measured and kept at room temperature for 15 h, then diluted with a mixture of cold distilled water (up to 13 cm³). In a sealed tube, the solution was further hydrolyzed by heating in a boiling water bath for 6h. The hydrolysate solution was then neutralized by adding a calculated amount of BaCO₃. The neutralized solution was filtered and thoroughly washed with water. The filtrate would be treated by a cation exchange resin (Amberlit IR-120 (H⁺)). The total amount of carbohydrates was determined in the extract using the phenol–sulfuric acid method. The details of this method are as follows: after suitable dilution, 1 cm³ of 5% phenol solution was added to 1 cm³ of the resulting diluted solution. After mixing, 5 cm³ of concentrated H₂SO₄ was added rapidly to the mixture, shaken, and set aside for 10 min at room temperature, then placed in a water bath at 20–30 °C for 20 min. Thereafter, the colour density was measured at 490 nm using a spectrophotometer.

2.4 Acid hydrolysis

The hydrolysis of the substrates was carried out according to the method reported [9] with slight modification. Exactly 100 g each of the ground substrates were transferred into a 500 ml beaker and mixed with 400 ml of 2 M H₂SO₄. The mixture was heated on a magnetic stirrer for 105 min at 90°C. The pH of the hydrolyzed samples was maintained at 6.5 by adding drops of 0.2 M sodium hydroxide solution and monitored using pH meter.

2.5 Fermentation of the hydrolysates

The fermentation method used for this study research was that reported [10] with slight modification. Yeast was first activated by mixing 3 g of the powdered yeast with 15 ml of water and 2 ml of the hydrolysed samples. The mixture was added to the samples for fermentation to take place and the resulting mixture was kept at room temperature for 3 days. Finally, the broths were transferred into conical flasks and airtight with cotton, aluminium foil and masking tape.

2.6 Distillation of the fermented samples

The fermented substrates otherwise called broths was recovered from the fermentation stage, the bioethanol in the form of azeotrope was obtained through distillation with use of rotary evaporator at 78.60 g of zeolite 4A was added to azeotrope and then stirred until the homogeneous mixture was formed this had been repeated three times in order to remove the water content from the azeotrope solution and obtain a high purity bioethanol.

2.7 Physicochemical Analysis of Bioethanol

2.7.1 Determination of ethanol yield (%)

The percentage yield of the bioethanol is determined using equation 4:

$$\% \text{yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of ethanol}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 4$$

2.7.2 Determination of pH of the produced bioethanol distillates

The pH of the bioethanol distillates from the three samples was determined using by introducing the probe of a digital pH meter into each distillate and taking the reading, each time, rinsing the probe with distilled water before introducing into a distillate. This was done for three replicate determinations.

2.7.3 Determination of Colour of the produced bioethanol distillates

The colour of the produced bioethanol of the samples was observed physically with the naked eyes [11].

2.7.4 Determination of specific gravity of produced bioethanol distillates

An empty bottle was placed on weighing balance and the reading was recorded, the bottle was removed and filled with 10 cm³ of the distillate which was later placed on a weighing balance, the reading was taken. The bottle was then removed and filled with 20 cm³ distilled water. The reading was recorded and the specific gravity was calculated using equation 5 [11].

Specific gravity =

$$\frac{\text{Weight of bottle + sample} - \text{weight of empty bottle}}{\text{Weight of bottle + water} - \text{weight of empty bottle}} \dots\dots\dots 5$$

2.7.5 Viscosity test

About 10 cm³ of bioethanol was turned into A-arm of tube capillary viscometer through the orifices to the marked point; a sucker was used to lift the sample to the b-arm of the capillary to the marked point. A stop watch was used to regulate the time it took the bioethanol to return (flow) to the mark under the B-arm and the time noted. Viscosity calibration curve was then used to convert viscosity in seconds to centistokes [12].

2.7.6 Boiling point

Boiling point is the temperature at which the vapor pressure is equal to atmospheric pressure and was determined by noting the reading of the inserted thermometer through the cork covering the conical flask containing the sample being heated.

2.8 Fuel Properties of Produced Bioethanol Distillates

2.8.1 Determination of flash point

This test was carried out using Pensky-Martens flash point apparatus. The cup in the apparatus was dried. 5 cm³ of each sample (ethanol produced) was transferred into the position in the apparatus assembled with thermometer and the apparatus was switched on, the heat was controlled by a steady stirrer to maintain a uniform temperature while passing a small flame across the material every five seconds. The temperature at which the

vapor first flashes with the blue flame was recorded as the flash point of the samples after each test cup was washed and dried before the subsequent test [12].

2.8.2 Determination pour point

The pour point of the obtained bioethanol from the samples was determined as described [11]. A portion of the bio-ethanol was poured into a test tube and the mercury point of the thermometer with calibration below 10 °C was inserted in the test tube. The set up was inserted in a beaker containing ice and left to solidify. When the solidification was confirmed, the test tube was removed and tilted and closely observed till it started to flow. The lowest temperature at which the sample was observed to flow was recorded as the pour point.

2.8.3 Determination of cloud point

A portion of bio-ethanol was poured into a test tube and the mercury point of the thermometer with calibration below 10 °C was inserted in the test tube. The set up was inserted in a beaker containing ice. The bio-ethanol was observed closely. After some time the bio-ethanol was observed to form a cloud of gel. The temperature was recorded as the cloud point [11].

2.8.4 FTIR Characterisation

The FT-IR spectrum of produced ethanol was recorded on Nicolet IR spectrometer at room temperature. The blending was done with potassium bromide (KBr) powder, and then for measurement these were pressed into tablets. The transmittance was recorded over a wave number range from 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

2.9 Statistical data analysis and presentation

The results were expressed as the mean, standard error of the mean (SEM), and coefficient of variation of each species for each parameter was determined. Data were statistically analyzed (SPSS statistical software 3.4.1) by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Mean comparisons were performed using Duncan's multiple range tests for significant effect at P < 0.05.

3.0 Results and Discussion

watermelon rinds and doum palm shells) are shown in Table 1.

3.1 Proximate Composition of Bioethanol Produced from Sweet Potato Peels, Watermelon Rinds and Doum Palm Shells

The results of proximate analysis of the three different substrates (sweet potato peels,

Table 1: Proximate Composition of Sweet Potato Peels, Watermelon Rinds and Doum Palm Shells

Parameter (%)	Samples		
	SPP	WMR	DPS
Moisture content	13.00±0.29 ^b	15.50±0.29 ^c	11.50±0.27 ^a
Ash content	17.00±0.46 ^b	18.00±0.69 ^b	7.50±0.23 ^a
Crude protein	3.68±0.09 ^a	5.43±0.12 ^b	3.33±0.23 ^a
Crude fibre	20.00±0.69 ^b	15.50±0.64 ^a	25.00±1.22 ^c
Carbohydrates	51.32±1.22 ^b	32.57±0.91 ^a	67.18±1.71 ^c

KEY: SPP= sweet potato peels; WMR= watermelon rinds; DPS= doum palm shells. Values were presented as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of three replicates. Values with different superscripts across row are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Ash content reflects the mineral content of a sample. In this study, the ash content of sweet potato peels and watermelon rinds showed no significant difference ($p < 0.05$), but both were significantly different ($p > 0.05$) from that of doum palm shells. The recorded values were 17.00% for sweet potato peels, 18.00% for watermelon rinds, and 7.50% for doum palm shells. The ash content range of 6.47% to 6.98% reported for palm fruit shells [14] is lower than the 7.50% found for doum palm shells in this study. Additionally, the 18.00% ash content for watermelon rinds is lower than the 97.93% reported [15].

Moisture content refers to the amount of water present in a food sample and affects its shelf life and susceptibility to spoilage [16]. The moisture content among the samples differed significantly ($p < 0.05$). The values recorded were 13.00% for sweet potato peels, 15.50% for watermelon rinds, and 11.50% for doum palm shells. Abdullahi et al. [17] previously reported a moisture content of 4.05% in sweet potato peels, which is lower than the 13.00% found in this study. Additionally, the highest moisture content for watermelon rinds in

this research is lower than the 99.82% reported [15].

The ratios of essential amino acids, which humans need but that animals cannot synthesize, influence the nutritional quality of proteins [18]. All living organisms rely on proteins for cellular structure, regulation of metabolic processes, and other vital functions. As a result, proteins play a crucial role in the daily diets of consumers [19]. In this study, the crude protein contents measured were 3.68% for sweet potato peels, 5.43% for watermelon rinds, and 3.33% for doum palm shells. Abdullahi et al. [17] reported a crude protein content of 5.61%, while Yargamji et al. [20] noted 2.79%, both of which are lower than the values found in this research.

The crude fiber values recorded in this study were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from each other. Specifically, the values were 20.00 %, 15.50 %, and 25.00 % for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. The crude fiber content of 10.60% and 12.54%, reported [20] for watermelon rinds and orange

peels, is lower than the values found in this study. Consuming foods rich in fiber promotes cardiovascular health, may help prevent colon cancer, and supports a healthy body weight while maintaining proper digestive [21].

The carbohydrate contents of the samples showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). The values observed were 51.32%, 32.57%, and 67.18% for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. Adegbehingbe and Adeleke [22] reported a carbohydrate content of

56.1% for cassava peels, which is higher than the 51.32% found for sweet potato peels in this study. Additionally, the carbohydrate content of 72.42% for watermelon rinds, as reported [20], exceeds the highest value of 67.18% observed for doum palm shells in this study.

3.2 Physicochemical properties of Produced Bioethanol Distillates

The physicochemical properties of produced bioethanol distillates are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Physicochemical Properties of Bioethanol Produced from Sweet Potato Peels (SPP), Watermelon Rinds

Sample	Percentage yield (%)	pH	Viscosity (mm^2/s)	Colour	Specific gravity
SPP	14.00±0.61 ^a	7.60±0.61 ^b	151.00±2.31 ^b	Colourless	0.99±0.00 ^a
WMR	29.40±0.72 ^c	7.15±0.72 ^a	196.00±1.73 ^c	Colourless	0.99±0.00 ^a
DPS	21.60±0.89 ^b	7.63±0.89 ^b	132.00±2.89 ^a	Colourless	0.99±0.00 ^a
ASTM bioethanol standard [13]			1.20	Colourless	0.87

Key: SPP= Sweet Potato Peels; WMR= Watermelon Rinds; DPS= Doum Palm Shells. Values were presented as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of three replicates. Values with different superscripts along column are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

The bioethanol yield of the samples was determined to be 14.00±0.61 %, 29.40±0.72 %, and 21.60±0.89 % for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. Significantly differing yields were observed ($P < 0.05$), with watermelon rinds displaying the highest percentage yield. The percentage yield for the samples in this investigation is lower than the 52% reported for snot apple [23] and the 86% for maize cob [11].

The findings of this study revealed significantly different ($p < 0.05$) specific gravity values of 0.99±0.00 gcm^3 , 0.99±0.00 gcm^3 , and 0.99±0.00 gcm^3 for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. This outcome mirrors the findings of Omoruyi et al. [24], where bioethanol derived from cassava and yam peels exhibited specific gravity values of 0.98 gcm^3 and 0.99 gcm^3 , respectively, employing different acid concentrations. Additionally, the specific gravity value obtained in this study slightly exceeds the 0.737 gcm^3 value reported for petrol [25]. It is recognized that bioethanol typically possesses a lower heating value than petrol due to the substantial presence of oxygen, yet bioethanol exhibits a higher specific gravity [26].

The boiling points of the bioethanol obtained from the samples exhibited significant differences

($p < 0.05$). Sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells displayed boiling points of 73.60 °C, 78.00 °C, and 62.80 °C, respectively. The boiling point of bioethanol derived from watermelon rinds (78.00 °C) in this investigation aligns closely with the 78.5 °C boiling point reported for bioethanol obtained from Christ's thorn Jujube Seeds (*Ziziphus spina-christi*) [27] and the 79.00 °C boiling point for both rotten watermelon and banana [28]. Moreover, the findings from this study suggest that the bioethanol obtained from watermelon rinds contains relatively fewer impurities compared to the bioethanol from sweet potato and doum palm shells.

The bioethanol derived from the samples exhibited significant differences ($p < 0.05$) among them. The findings indicated viscosity values of 151.00±2.31 mm^2/s , 196.00±1.73 mm^2/s , and 132.00±2.89 mm^2/s for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. These values exceed the viscosity thresholds of 1.3 mm^2/s and 1.2 mm^2/s reported for Matoke species [29] and are also higher than the viscosity range of petrol, which typically falls between 0.37 – 0.44 mm^2/s [30]. The values also exceed 1.20 which is the ASTM standard.

The pH of the bioethanol distillates for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells were 7.60, 7.15 and 7.63 respectively. There was significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the pH of water melon rinds and those of potato peels and doum palm. However, the pH of potato peels and doum palm shells showed no significant difference.

The bioethanol distillates produced from the substrates were colorless. Typically, bioethanol is a clear liquid, though it may show color if

contaminated with heavy metals or microorganisms [31].

3.3 Fuel Properties of Produced Bioethanol Distillates

The fuel properties of the bioethanol produced from sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds and doum palm shells are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Fuel Properties of Bioethanol Produced from Sweet Potato Peels, Watermelon Rinds and Doum Palm Shells

Sample	Flash point (°C)	Pour point (°C)	Cloud point (°C)	Boiling point (°C)
SPP	55.20±1.23 ^b	-4.60±0.03 ^a	-6.92±0.06 ^c	73.60±1.24 ^b
WMR	47.60±0.85 ^a	-4.10±0.02 ^b	-7.75±0.02 ^a	78.00±1.07 ^c
DPS	45.90±0.57 ^a	-3.96±0.02 ^c	-7.11±0.02 ^b	62.80±1.16 ^a
ASTM standard [13]	18.60	5.20	23.00	78.00

Key: SPP = Sweet Potato Peels; WMR= Watermelon Rinds; DPS= Doum Palm Shells. Values were presented as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of three replicates. Values with different superscripts along column are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

The findings revealed significant variations ($p < 0.05$) in the cloud point values of the samples. The observed cloud point values were -6.92 °C, -7.75 °C, and -7.11 °C for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells, respectively. These values are slightly lower than -6.00 °C cloud point reported for snot apple [23] and are slightly higher than the -11.00 °C cloud point obtained for maize cob [11]. The results suggest that bioethanol derived from watermelon rinds exhibited the most favorable cloud point (-7.75 °C), although it remains higher than that of petrol, which is -18 °C [23].

The pour points of the analyzed samples exhibited significant differences ($p < 0.05$). Sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells displayed pour point values of -4.60±0.03 °C, -4.10±0.02 °C, and -3.96±0.02 °C,

respectively. These values exceed those reported for maize cob (-13.00 °C) and Abrus seed (-17.00 °C) [32, 11]. Additionally, the pour points of the samples exceed the -22 °C pour point for petrol [23]. This suggests that decreasing the pour points may be necessary to enhance their fuel potential.

The flash point bioethanol from sweet potato peels was significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from those of watermelon rinds and doum palm shells, which were not different from each other. The flash points bioethanol obtained from the substrates were 55.20 °C, 47.60 °C and 45.90 °C for sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds and doum palm shells respectively. These values are however, higher than 12.8 °C for Nigerian palm bunch and petrol (-69 °C) as reported [33].

3.4 FTIR Characterization of Bioethanol

Table 4: FTIR Analysis of Bioethanol from Sweet Potato Peels, Watermelon Rinds and Doum Palm Shells

Functional Group	SPP (cm ⁻¹)	WMR (cm ⁻¹)	DPS (cm ⁻¹)
O-H	3265	3257	3301
C-H (stretching)	2109	2112	1985
C=O	1636	1638	1610

Key: SPP= Sweet Potato Peels; WMR= Watermelon Rinds; DPS= Doum Palm Shells

FTIR analysis of the bioethanol produced from the samples identified key functional groups: broad peaks between 3257 cm^{-1} and 3301 cm^{-1} , indicating hydroxyl (O-H) group stretching for alcohol; absorption peaks between 1985 cm^{-1} and 2109 cm^{-1} , corresponding to C-H stretching; and peaks observed between 1610 cm^{-1} and 1638 cm^{-1} , signifying the presence of the carbonyl (C=O) group. These findings align with those reported in previous studies on bioethanol [34, 35].

4.0 Conclusion

This study compared the proximate composition and bioethanol production potential of three substrates: sweet potato peels, watermelon rinds, and doum palm shells. The substrates were found to contain significant amounts of proximate components such as ash, moisture, crude protein, crude fiber, and carbohydrates, with watermelon rinds showing the highest levels. FTIR analysis of the distilled bioethanol confirmed the presence of alcohol. The physicochemical and fuel properties of the bioethanol distillates—such as pour point, specific gravity, flash point, cloud point, and boiling point—suggest that the substrates, particularly watermelon rinds (with a 29% yield), could be viable sources of bioethanol.

5.0 Recommendations

It was recommended that the bioethanol produced from the substrates should be blended with petrol/diesel and the fuel properties investigated.

6.0 Acknowledgements

The authors wish to acknowledge the immense contributions of Dr. Ibrahim Sani Shabanda, Dr. Abdulaziz Mohammed Hassan, Dr. Cosmos MokiElinge and Prof. Yusuf Haruna of Department Of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Kebbi State University Of Science and Technology, Aliero.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

8.0 References

[1] Gupta AP, Upadhyay P, Sen T, Dutta J. Agricultural Waste as a Resource: The Lesser Travelled Road to Sustainability. Agriculture Waste Management and

Bioresource: The Circular Economy Perspective. 2023; 20:1-20.

[2] Maji S, Dwivedi DH, Singh N, Kishor S, Gond M. Agricultural waste: Its impact on environment and management approaches. Emerging Eco-Friendly Green Technologies for Wastewater Treatment. 2020; 329-351.

[3] Banga KS, Kumar S. Agricultural waste to wealth. Agriculture & Food: e-Newsletter, 2019; 27.

[4] Kandpal R, Singh R. Renewable Energy Sources—A Review. ECS Transactions, (2022); 107(1):8133.

[5] Capanoglu E, Nemli E, Tomas-Barberan F. Novel approaches in the valorization of agricultural wastes and their applications. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 2022; 70(23):6787-6804.

[6] Usman A, Jonathan LA, Lawal MM, Onotu MK. Investigation of subsurface structural competence for building foundation in Kebbi State University of Science and Technology Aliero. Science.2020;(1):44-53.

[7] AOAC (2018), Official method of Analysis, 17th edition, Association of Analytical Chemist. Gaithersburg, MD, USA. 624-642.

[8] Ragab TI, Alminderej FM, El-Sayed WA, Saleh SM, Shalaby AS. Enhanced Optimization of Bioethanol Production from Palm Waste Using the Taguchi Method. Sustainability. 2021 Dec 10;13(24):13660.

[9] Rabi A, Elinge C, Ambursa M, Rabi A, Samaila D. Characterization of Bioethanol Fuel from Rice and Corn Straws: A Comparative Study. Equity J. Sci. Technol. 2021; 8: 74-78.

[10] Ahmad MA, Tambuwal AD, Sokoto AM, Sanda A. delignification pretreatment of *acanthus permum* hispidum biomass for bioethanol production. FUDMA Journal of Sciences. 2023;7(5):281-7.

[11] Harrison O, Ekene C, Nathaniel I. Production and Characterization of Bioethanol from

- Acid Catalysed Hydrolysis of Cellulosic Biomass (Maize Cob). *J. Energy Environ. Chem. Eng.* 2022 Jul;7:66-70.
- [12] Maina MB, Oluwole FA, Ngala GM, Abdulrahman SA. Comparison of the properties and yield of bioethanol from mango and orange waste. *Arid Zone Journal of Engineering, Technology and Environment.* 2017;13(6):779.
- [13] Saka AA., Afolabi AS, Ogochukwu MU. Production and characterization of bioethanol from sugarcane bagasse as alternative energy sources. In 2015 World Congress on Engineering, WCE 2015.2015; 876-880. Newswood Limited.
- [14] Inegbedion F. Estimation of the moisture content, volatile matter, ash content, fixed carbon and calorific values of palm fruit shells briquettes. *Int. J. Adv. Res. Sci. Eng. Technol.* 2021;8(6):17551-5.
- [15] Ebelegi AN, Toneth EI, Bokizibe MA. Determination of Physicochemical Properties of Biosorbents Synthesized from Water Melon Rinds Using Microwave Assisted Irradiation Procedure. *Open Journal of Physical Chemistry.* 2022 May 31;12(02):19-30.
- [16] Saleem Z, Khan MH, Ahmad M, Sohaib A, Ayaz H, Mazzara M. Prediction of microbial spoilage and shelf-life of bakery products through hyperspectral imaging. *IEEE Access.* 2020 Sep 25;8:176986-96.
- [17] Abdullahi AI, Mohammed T, Lalai W, Hassan NMZ, Ibrahim Y. Proximate composition, mineral content and anti-nutrient of raw and sun-dried sweet potato peels. *ASUU Journal of Sci.* 2021;8(1):1-14.
- [18] Brestenský M, Nitravová S, Patráš P, Nitrav J. Dietary requirements for proteins and amino acids in human nutrition. *Current Nutrition & Food Science.* 2019;15(7):638-45.
- [19] Yu YM, Fukagawa NK. Protein and amino acids. In *Present knowledge in nutrition* 2020 Jan 1 (pp. 15-35). Academic Press.
- [20] Yargamji GI., Adamu U, Abubakar, T. Comparative studies on the proximate, mineral and energy contents of watermelon and orange peels. *Journal of African Resilience and Advancement Research.* 2024;3(2), 1-20.
- [21] Hussein S, Xiaoying Y, Farouk MH, Abdeen A, Hussein A, Hailong J. The role effects of dietary fiber on intestinal microbial composition and digestive physiological functions of pigs: A review. *Indian Journal of Animal Research.* 2021; 55(7):737-43.
- [22] Adegbehingbe T, Adeleke B. Bioethanol production from Cassava peels inoculated with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Zymomonas mobilis*. *Journal of Advances in Microbiology.* 2021;21(9):58-67.
- [23] Abioye AM. Production and characterization of bioethanol from snot apple (*Azanzagarckeana*). *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM).* 2022;4(1):447-456.
- [24] Omoruyi U, Odogwu CA, Asworth VO, Sama FJ, Aiwonegbe AE, Ogbeide OK, Unuigbo CA, Irabor EE. Comparative study on bioethanol production from agro-waste feedstock via acid hydrolysis method using two different mineral acids as catalyst. *Chem Search Journal.* 2022;13(2):117-23.
- [25] Koay LK, Sah MJ, bin Othman R. Comparative study of fuel consumption, acceleration and emission for road vehicle using LPG or gasoline. *Advanced engineering for processes and technologies.* 2019:77-87.
- [26] Toor M, Kumar SS, Malyan SK., Bishnoi NR, Mathimani T, Rajendran K., Pugazhendhi A.. An overview on bioethanol production from lignocellulosic feedstocks. *Chemosphere.* 2020;242:1-12.
- [27] Sintali I, Saidu S, Makwin F, Aliyu N, Isaac L. Analysis of Physico-Chemical Properties of Christ Thorn Jujube Seeds (*Ziziphus Spina-Christi*) Bioethanol-Gasoline Blends. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals.* 2023;7(3):430-436.
- [28] Saad AB, Musa DD, Muhammad FT. Production of Bioethanol from Rotten

- Watermelon (*Citrulluslanatus*) and Banana (*Musa sapientum*) Using Enzymatic Approach. *Sahel Journal of Life Sciences FUDMA*. 2023;1(1):163-8.
- [29] Yusuf AA, Inambao FL. Bioethanol production from different Matookepeelss species: a surprising source for alternative fuel. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. (2019);13:1-10.
- [30] Yusuf AA, Inambao FL. Progress in alcohol-gasoline blends and their effects on the performance and emissions in SI engines under different operating conditions. *Internal Journal of Ambient Energy*, 2018; 1-41.
- [31] Hashmi M, Hameed A. Bioethanol production from sugarcane molasses an industrial waste product. *National Journal of Biological Science*. 2020;1: 01-23.
- [32] Obeta JC, Ossai EC, Njoku OU. Optimization and characterization of bioethanol production from Abrus seed flour. *International journal of energy research*. 2021;45:(3), 3883-3898.
- [33] Igbokwe JO, Onuoha LN, Nwafor MOI, Aviara NA. Characterization of blends of petrol and bioethanol synthesized from Nigerian palm bunch. *Arid Zone Journal of Engineering, Technology and Environment*, 2019; 15(1):142-152.
- [34] Sakar D, Prajapati S, Poddar K., Sarkar A. Production of ethanol by *Enterobacter*sp. EtK3 during fruit waste biotransformation. *Int. Biodeter Biodegrad*. 2019;145:104795.
- [35] Nagenderan S, Rajamamundi P, Chandran M, Gopinath KP. Bioethanol from *Moringa oleifera* and pithecellobiumdulce leafs: Production and characterization. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*. 2020;42(1):66-72.

BY

Copyright © 2024 by the authors. This article is an open access article under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice.